

ON THE ISSUE OF MUTUAL INFLUENCE OF ENGLISH AND RUSSIAN LANGUAGES

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ABSTRACT

In recent years, there has been a process of globalization, during which differences between cultures are gradually being erased, which leads to an increase in contacts between peoples, which, among other things, implies the mutual influence of languages. Considering that English has become the language of international communication, we are often talking about the mutual influence of English and national languages, in which, as a rule, the first plays a dominant role. In this regard, the work examines the mutual influence of English and Russian languages at the lexical level.

Unusual similarity between English and Russian words. Is not it? Indeed, some words in English and Russian are very similar in sound, spelling and have a common meaning. The question arises: "Why are they so similar?" Turning to the English-Russian dictionary, you can see that there are a lot of such words, and they differ in the ending or suffix inherent in a given language. For example, knit - нитки, band - банда, sheet - щит, table - таблица, mooch - мучиться, sedate - сесть. In this regard, the purpose of our study was to identify the degree of similarity between the English and Russian languages.

It is known that there are groups of languages, the kinship within which has tangible practical significance. Knowing one language in a group makes it possible to partially understand, or at least easily learn to understand, others. There are also broader groups within which kinship is of scientific interest only. American linguist M. Swadesh proposed a scale characterizing the degree of relatedness of languages. The definitions of this scale are based on the percentage of common vocabulary in the two languages, from which the age of their separation can be calculated. M. Swadesh considers speech forms to be the same language if the percentage of common words in them corresponds to an age not exceeding 500 years.

Another scale was developed by Russian researcher S.E. Yakhontov. It is based not only on the age principle of linguistic differences, but also on the degree of mutual understanding between speakers of the two languages. According to this scale, there are 6 degrees of similarity between languages. Let us present a brief description of each of them.

1st degree. The smallest linguistic differences noticeable to speakers: speakers of different idioms communicate freely with each other, but by the peculiarities of pronunciation and partly vocabulary they can approximately determine where each of them comes from. The approximate time of divergence of such languages is 200 years. Examples include dialects of Russian and English.

2nd degree. Speakers of different idioms communicate with each other without much difficulty; isolated cases of misunderstanding are possible. For example, such a relationship exists between the Ukrainian and Russian languages. The divergence time of such linguistic units is 500 years.

3rd degree. Speakers of different idioms cannot communicate freely, but they constantly hear familiar words and even short phrases in each other's speech. A speaker of one language can learn to understand another, "gradually getting used to it" without a textbook or translator. For example, native speakers of Russian and Bulgarian, or Italian and Spanish. The divergence time here, accordingly, is much longer - 1000 - 1500 years.

4th degree. Communication is impossible, but with the systematic study of languages we discover many common words and grammar rules (Russian and Lithuanian languages). Similar languages diverged about 2000 years ago.

5th degree. Only a specialist can discover the relationship between two languages. Words that appear common are most likely recent borrowings from one language to another or from a common source. It seems possible to compare not all words of the linguistic layer, but the most significant or frequent words of some special layers of vocabulary. For example, numerals, pronouns, names of family relationships, parts of the face, luminaries, some animals. Such languages separated from each other even earlier - 3000-4000 years ago.

6th degree. Sometimes evidence of a common origin is very scanty. The structure of the compared languages in their modern state is very different, lexical matches are rare, common words often have different meanings, and only roots go back to the parent language.

Having studied the existing degrees of similarity of languages, we can say that the similarity of the Russian and English languages is determined by the 5th degree of relationship. By comparing the stable layers of vocabulary of these languages, we can easily find pairs of words that not only have a common origin, but also to some extent retain a similar phonetic appearance. For example, three – три, my – мой, brother – брат, nose – нос, sun – солнце. There are significant differences in the structure of these two languages, but many grammatical features characteristic of the Russian language have been preserved in English, at least as isolated remnants.

We propose to analyze a number of consonant words, paying attention to their semantic meaning. So, очки are translated into English as glasses. The word is very similar to the Russian "eyes". Undoubtedly, the kinship of languages can be traced, because glasses represent second eyes. "очки" - "glasses", i.e. "малые очи" As for the consonance of words, this is not surprising in closely related European languages. That's what "relatives" are for, to be like each other.

Let's take for example a couple of words money - деньги. The English word money is familiar and understandable to everyone. But few people know that it has Slavic roots and comes from the word мены, that is, "what is exchanged for". There is a word in Russian called монеты (coins).

The following words are of no less interest: clock- часы. The English word clock does not mean any clock, but only wall, table and tower clocks. All these types of clocks inherited their name from the first clock of mankind - the solar clock. Their core is a rod that casts a shadow. Simply put колышек, околосок or клосок (a small stake). It is from this word that the English word clock, o'clock comes from.

Another example is the ancient Russian-Slavic word лан, meaning land, territory. It is found in the word Russolania, i.e. Land of the Russians. The English language also has this word land - earth, so now we translate England - Land of the Angles, which corresponds to English history. The English word wall is translated as стена. And in the Old Russian language the word волъ had two meanings - earthen embankment and sea shaft, wave. The complete coincidence of the roots and meanings of these words is obvious.

What are the main ways in which common words appear in Russian and English:

Firstly, the commonality between the grammatical and lexical properties of the Russian and English languages is determined by their common membership in the Indo-European family and is manifested in the presence of common grammatical meanings, categories and functions. Therefore, in many words of both languages there are roots from their common ancient parent language. These words were not borrowed, they were originally common. One is often surprised at what "original Russian" words are also found in English.

The many consonances among the most important words of the language remind us of the former linguistic community and kinship of the Russian and English languages. Among them: cheek - щека, water - вода, milk - молоко, sister - сестра, salt - соль, day - день, daughter - дочь, cat - кот.

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Secondly, a large number of common Russian and English words are derived from Greek and Latin roots. It is known that in the Middle Ages Latin was the international language of scientists; through it a huge number of words passed into all European languages and became international. Almost all terminology in medicine and many other sciences goes back to Latin: куб - cube, квадрат - quadrangle, сфера - sphere, эллипс - ellipse, антибиотик - antibiotic, бактериофаг - bacteriophage and etc.

In addition, many common words came into Russian and English from other languages. The first place here, of course, is occupied by French, which was spoken by all the Russian nobility in the XIX century. From them many French words passed into the Russian language. Many words have entered international use from other languages, and they have become common to Russian and English. We remember that classical music was formed in Italy. It is from there that the concepts of the basic elements and expressive means of music, the names of its genres, tempos, etc. were accepted by all European languages: опера - opera, ария - aria, бас - bass,

адажио - adagio, etc. Words such as банк – bank, бригада - brigade, архипелаг - archipelago, казино - casino etc. also came from Italian.

It is difficult for us to speak about Russian words in English. The Webster's Dictionary of the American Language lists Russian words such as borscht, pancake, balalaika, ataman, artel, etc., but it is not clear to what extent they have actually come into use and how actively they are used. Some examples can be given confidently. The word bistro is called French in dictionaries, but we know that Russian soldiers brought it to Paris in 1814. Karakul in English is called astrakhan, after the name of the Russian city of Astrakhan, from where, apparently, these skins were brought.

It is also sometimes difficult to identify native English words within the Russian language, since it is usually unknown whether a word came to us from English or came to both languages from Latin or some other language. Therefore, we can speak with confidence only about words that entered the Russian language relatively recently. For example, football came to us from England with all its terminology like goal, penalty, forward, out, etc.

Recently, the Russian language has been experiencing a large influx of new English words. Life in Russia is changing rapidly, new economic relations are emerging. New words were needed to describe new concepts, and many of them come from English. The introduction of English words is also facilitated by the widespread use of computers, since all terminology in this area is English.

Many linguists are sounding the alarm about the contamination of the Russian language with foreign words. However, you should not resist this process. Language is a living organism; it will digest some new words and turn them into its own, and discard the rest.

At the end of the work, I would like to quote from Boris Vasiliev's work "Prophetic Oleg":
"We have a common root, voivode."

- Yes, the root is common, but everyone has their own fruits.

This statement fully applies to languages. Often words from different languages have a similar root, but differ in form and, in some cases, semantic content.

During the study, it was revealed that not every coincidence can serve as evidence of the relationship of languages. In modern languages, many lexical units appeared as a result of borrowing from Latin and other languages and are therefore characterized by the presence of a common root. The primordial relationship of languages implies the development from one more or less unified language that existed previously. And borrowings are the result of contacts of languages. If more or less systematic material similarities are observed in any languages, it does not indicate contacts and borrowings, but the primordial kinship of the corresponding languages, that these languages come from the same language, are different historical "continuations", reincarnations of one and the same language. the same language that was once in use.

As for the degree of kinship between the Russian and English languages, it can be said with confidence that their kinship goes back to the distant past. Signs of similarity are not observed in all linguistic layers. It is not always possible to trace coincidences with the development and change of languages. Without knowledge of the history of the development of languages, it is difficult to restore their common roots. Only a specialist can determine the relationship of these languages. The fact that these languages contain a large number of similar-sounding words is explained by borrowing from one language to another and from a common source. Original

kinship can be traced only in some layers of vocabulary, which are characterized by great stability.

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